

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL CREATIVITY LEVELS AND PROBLEM-SOLVING ABILITIES OF SPORT İSTANBUL MANAGERS

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to examine the relationship between organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities of senior and mid-level sports managers working in Istanbul Sports Activities and Business Trading Corporation. Relational screening model which is used to determine the relationship between variables is applied. In the direction of the aim of the research, target population of the study is composed of senior and mid-level managers working in İstanbul Sports Activities and Business Trading Corporation; the sample designed by simple random sampling method is composed of volunteer sports managers (n=98). Personal information form, organizational creativity scale and "Problem Solving Inventory" designed by Heppner and Petersen (1982), adapted to Turkish by Şahin and Heppner (1993) are applied to participants. The obtain data are recorded by "IBM SPSS 22" packaged software. As statistical processing, Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis are used. As a result, it is determined that the organizational creativity of the sport managers is at a high level, problem solving abilities are inadequate, and there is a negative relationship between

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organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities, and organizational creativity level predicts problem solving abilities.

Keywords: sport manager, organizational creativity, problem solving ability

1. Introduction

It is conditional for organizations to determine and plan for the differences that cause "economic, technological, and social factors" in order to maintain continuity and achieve targeted success. It is necessary to have innovative ways and methods in an environment where competition in the international and national arena is increasing, technology develops rapidly, and individuals have different expectations. To deal with this situation, thinking creatively, increasing new product and service options, and providing good service quality become compulsory. In other words, businesses focusing on theory need to open to innovation and change to be successful in the application parts and competitive environment (Kwasniewska and Neck, 2004). In order to develop creativity, there is a need for open and flexible work environments (Stoner and Wankel, 1986). The development of organizational perception and creativity levels of people increase sense of wonder and engaging with problems within the institution by providing them new living and experiences (Yahşi, 2014). Organizational creativity is a valuable, beneficial, new product, service, idea or process developed by individuals working in organizations (Woodman, Sawyer and Griffin, 1993). One of the most important tasks of senior managers in organizations is to support the process of creativity and to remove the obstacles in this process because creativity in organizations is "a human-specific process of thought oriented to produce new ideas that can be beneficial for solving existing problems" (Martins, and Terblanche, 2003).

Managing this process efficiently facilitates problem solutions and also develops problem solving abilities of managers and staff. Problem-solving ability is a skill to reach information that leads individual to solve problems and to apply this information to problem solving by operationalizing it (Bahar, 2006). Negative internal and external environments of organizations motivate managers to investigate, obtain information and take measures. Thus, the desire of individuals to be open to change and innovation in organizations can contribute to problem solving and organizational creativity level of managers. The aim of this research is to examine the relationship between organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities of senior and middle level sports managers working in Istanbul Sports Activities and Business Trading Corporation

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Creation of Volunteer Group

Target population of the study is composed of senior and mid-level managers working in İstanbul Sports Activities and Business Trading Corporation; the sample designed by simple random sampling method is composed of volunteer sports managers (n=98).

2.2. Data Collection Tools

2.2.1 Socio-Demographic Information Form

This form constituted by the researcher consists of 5 questions: sexuality, age, title, education level, and professional experience.

2.2.2 Organizational Creativity Scale

In the research, organizational creativity scale created by Balay (2010) is used in order to measure participants' organizational creativity level. The scale consists of 3 sub-dimensions as personal dimension (between 1.-16. items), supervisory dimension (between 17.-27. items), and social dimension (between 28.-38. items). As a result of reliability analysis done for organizational creativity scale, Balay (2010) found internal consistency coefficient of personal dimension as .92, reliability coefficient as, 947, supervisory dimension as .93, its reliability coefficient as, 947, social dimension as .95, its reliability coefficient as, 951. Scale items are graded as "Never" (1), "Rare" (2), "Average" (3), "Very" (4) and "Complete" (5) according to fivefold "Likert Scale" (Balay, 2010). Scale options and their points and limits are designed as Completely disagree (1.00-1.79), Slightly agree (1.80-2.59), Moderately agree (2.60-3.39), Mostly agree (3.40-4.19), Completely Agree (4.20-5.00).

2.3. Problem Solving Scale

"Problem Solving Inventory" designed by Heppner and Petersen (1982), adapted to Turkish by Şahin and Heppner (1993) in order to measure participants' problem solving levels are applied to participants. The scale consists of six sub-dimensions as "hotheaded approach" (13, 14, 15, 17, 21, 25, 26, 30 and 32. items, =0,78), "deliberative approach" (18, 20, 31, 33 and 35. items, =0,76), "avoidant approach" (1, 2, 3 and 4. items, = 0,74), "evaluative approach" (6, 7 and 8. items, =0,69), "self-confident approach" (5, 11, 23, 24, 27, 28 and 34. items, =0,64) and "planful approach" (10, 12, 16 and 19. items, =0,59). In the scale 9, 22, and 29. items is not included in grading, 1, 2, 3, 4, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 21, 25, 26, 30 and 34. items are graded reversely. It is assumed that these items represent sufficient problem-solving abilities. The score of the scale is between 32 and

192, and the average score of the scale is 80. The scores above the average indicate that individuals are not good at problem solving and the scores below the average score indicate that the individual is adequate in problem solving abilities (Şahin, Şahin and Heppner, 1993). The scale items are ranked according to six-fold "Likert Scale" as "I always act like that" (1), "I mostly act like that" (2), "I frequently act like that" (3), "I sometimes act like that" (4), "I rarely act like that" (5), "I never act like that" (6) (Savaşır and Şahin, 1997).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from personal information form, scales of organizational creativity and problem-solving ability are entered into SPSS22.0 packaged software and analyses are made via this program. The personal information, averages and factor scores for the candidates are determined by evaluating frequency (f) and percentage (%) values. In order to determine the parametric and non-parametric distribution of points; parametric and non-parametric distribution curves and skewness-kurtosis values are examined. The data show a parametric distribution. For statistical analysis, Pearson Correlation analysis is used for analyzing the relationship between organizational creativity and problem-solving abilities, and regression analysis is used for determining organizational creativity level on problem-solving ability

3. Results and Discussion

The participants' organizational creativity scale is found to be $4,01 \pm 0,49$ in the individual dimension average, $3,76 \pm 0,69$ in the managerial dimension average, $3,58 \pm 0,76$ in the social dimension average and $3,81 \pm 0,53$ in the organizational creativity average. The sports directors state that they highly agree regarding the answers of the questions that constitute the organizational creativity scale sub-dimension (3.40-4.19). It is observed that sport managers' organizational creativity perceptions are at a good level. However, the literature basically lacks regarding the studies on directors. In a study conducted by Yurter (2016), the organizational creativity behaviors of teachers are found to be high. The "problem solving abilities scale" subscales of the sport managers are $33,55 \pm 9,29$ for the "hotheaded approach" subscale score, $13,82 \pm 7,58$ for the "deliberative approach" subscale score, $16,08 \pm 6,53$ for the "avoidant approach" subscale score, $8,76 \pm 4,99$ for the "evaluative approach" subscale score, $20,38 \pm 7,24$ for the "self-confident approach" subscale score, $11,00 \pm 5,81$ for the "planful approach" subscale score, and $103,58 \pm 25,14$ for the problem-solving abilities total score. When the sub-dimensions are examined, it is seen that the "hotheaded approach", "self-confident

approach", "avoidant approach" and "deliberative approach" are the ones that the sport managers perceive themselves as inadequate, and that the "evaluative approach" and "planful approach" are sub-dimensions that managers perceive themselves better regarding the problem solving. When the literature is examined, in the study conducted by the managers of the hospitals by Çelik and Yurdakul (2009), it is seen that the sub-dimensions that the managers perceive themselves as inadequate are "hotheaded approach", "self-confident approach", "deliberative approach" and "planful approach", and that the sub-dimensions they perceive themselves better are "avoidant approach" and "evaluative approach". The overall average score of the managers taking part in the survey is 108.68. Tokat et al. (2005), in a study they conducted on the academics in Dumlupınar University, found the problem-solving skills sub-dimensions as 7.14 for "evaluative approach", 7.81 for the "deliberative approach", 8.10 for the "avoidant approach", 8.34 for the "planful approach", 12.63 for the "self-confident approach", and 24.19 for the "hotheaded approach". The total score of the inventory is between 32 and 192, while the average score is 80. The values above the average indicate that the person is not sufficient in problem solving, while the values below indicate that the person is adequate in problem solving (Şahin, Şahin and Heppner, 1993).

Gemlik and Sur (2004), in the study conducted with private hospital managers, found that the average score of the problem-solving abilities scale is 81.78 ± 6.68 . The studies in the literature are partially parallel however showing certain differences from our findings. That the problem-solving ability is higher than the general score ($103,58 \pm 25,14$) in the study makes possible to consider that the sports managers are inadequate in problem solving abilities, or they simply cannot perceive the problem. It has been determined that there is a moderately negative relationship between participants' organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities. As the level of organizational creativity of the sport managers increases, there is a decrease for a moderate degree in their problem-solving abilities. When literature is examined, it is seen that studies do not cover the relationship between organizational creativity and problem-solving abilities, however there are studies covering problem solving and decision-making styles, organizational creativity and school climate, organizational creativity and organizational climate perceptions in the literature (Dinçer, 2013; Yahşi 2014; Yurter 2014; Yurter 2016). In order to habilitate the problem-solving abilities of the sports managers, it requires a good level of organizational creativity for the sports managers, an open-mindedness of the sports managers regarding individual, managerial, and social renewals, an adaptation for an organizational culture, a motive for advancement in general, a participative culture and supportive approach regarding the whole members of the organization

The level of organizational creativity has a meaningful relationship with problem solving level. When the t-test results regarding the significance of the regression coefficient are examined, it is seen that "organizational creativity" total score is predictive on problem solving level and explains about 25% of the total variance. A similar study is not found when the literature is examined.

4. Conclusion

Consequently, it is determined that the organizational creativity of the sport managers is at a high level while their problem-solving abilities are inadequate. It is seen that there is a moderately negative relationship between organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities, and that organizational creativity level simply predicts problem solving abilities.

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Appendix

a. Figures and Tables

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Participants

		Frequency	Percentage
Sexuality	Female	34	34,7
	Male	64	65,3
	Total	98	100,0
Age	21-26	17	17,3
	27-32	33	33,7
	33-38	36	36,7
	39 and above	12	12,2
	Total	98	100,0
Level of Education	High School	48	49,0
	Undergraduate	44	44,9
	Graduate	6	6,1
	Total	98	100,0
Title	Manager	10	10,2
	Assistant Manager	9	9,2
	Department Manager	34	34,7
	Assistant Department Manager	45	45,9
	Total	98	100,0
Professional Experience	1-5 years	28	28,6
	6-10 years	30	30,6
	11 years and above	40	40,8
	Total	98	100,0

When Table 1 is examined, it was seen that 34.7% of the volunteers participating in the study are female, 65.3% of them are male; that 17.3% of them are between the ages of 21-26, 33.7% of them are between 27-32, 36.7% of them are between 33-38, and 12.2% of them are in the age 39 years and over; that 49.0% of them are in high school, 44.9% of them are undergraduate, 6.1% are graduate; that 10.2% of them are managers, 9.2% are assistant managers, 34.7% are department managers and 45.9% are assistant department managers; and finally that 28.6% of them have 1-5 years of work experience, 30.6% of them have 6-10 years work experience, and 40.8% of them have work experience of 11 years and over.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Participants' Answers to the Scale

		N	Min	Max	X±Sd
Organizational Creativity Ability	Personal Dimension	98	3,13	5,00	4,01±0,49
	Supervisory Dimension	98	2,00	5,00	3,76±0,69
	Social Dimension	98	1,73	5,00	3,58±0,76
	Total	98	2,47	5,00	3,81±0,53
Problem Solving Ability	Hotheaded Approach	98	14,00	54,00	33,55±9,29
	Deliberative Approach	98	5,00	30,00	13,82 ±7,58
	Avoidant Approach	98	4,00	24,00	16,08±6,53
	Evaluative Approach	98	3,00	18,00	8,76±4,99
	Self-Confident Approach	98	7,00	42,00	20,38±7,24
	Planful Approach	98	4,00	24,00	11,00±5,81
	Problem Solving Total	98	61,00	192,00	103,58±25,14

When Table 2 is examined; participants' organizational creativity scale personal dimension average is founded as 4,01±0,49, supervisory dimension average 3,76±0,69, social dimension average 3,58±0,76 and organizational creativity average 3,81±0,53. Problem solving ability scale hotheaded approach sub-dimension score is founded as 33,55±9,29, deliberative approach sub-dimension score as 13,82 ±7,58, avoidant approach sub-dimension score as 16,08±6,53, evaluator approach sub-dimension score as 8,76±4,99, self-confident approach sub-dimension score as 20,38±7,24, planned approach sub-dimension score as 11,00±5,81, and problem-solving total score as 103,58±25,14.

Table 3: The Relationship between Participants' Organizational Creativity Level and Problem-Solving Abilities of Participants

		1	2
Organizational Creativity Level	p	1	
	r	-	
Problem-Solving Ability	r	-,502	1
	p	,000	

When Table 3 is examined; it is seen that there is a moderately negative relationship between organizational creativity levels and problem-solving abilities of participants (r=,502, p<,001).

Table 4: Regression Analysis on Problem Solving Ability Prediction

	β	t	P	R	R ²	F	p
Fixed				,502	,252	20,572	,000
Organizational Creativity	,502	4,536	,000				

When Table 4 is examined, it states a significant relationship between organizational creativity level and problem-solving level ($R=,502$, $R^2=,252$; $p<,001$). When the t-test results regarding the significance of the regression coefficient are examined, it is seen that the "organizational creativity" total score ($t = 4,356$, $p = ,000$) predicts the problem-solving level and explains about 25% of the total variance.

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